

***Leucania putrescens* (Hübner, [1824]), a new member of the fauna
of Hungary (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)**

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Abstract – A female specimen of *Leucania putrescens* (Hübner, [1824]) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) from Kismaros (Pest County, Hungary) was found in the private collection of the late György Kutassy (1929–2017), representing the first record of the species from Hungary.

Key words – migrant, new record, faunistics

INTRODUCTION

György Kutassy (1929–2017) (SZABÓKY 2007) deceased on 5.VII.2017. Five years later, in 2022 the author has begun to compile the inventory of Gy. Kutassy's significant private entomological collection, resulting in the presently reported species new to the Hungarian fauna, as well as further results which are intended to be published in a separate paper.

RESULTS

Noctuidae

Leucania putrescens (Hübner, [1824])
(Fig. 1)

Material examined – During the compilation of the inventory of Gy. Kutassy's entomological collection, one female specimen of *Leucania putrescens* was found, previously misidentified as *Mythimna comma* (Linnaeus, 1761). Verbatim label data: “Mythimna comma, 1993.VIII.10., Kismaros, HUNGARY, leg Kutassy György”. The voucher specimen is deposited in the Hungarian Natural History Museum (HNHM, Budapest).

Remarks – This species is distributed in the Mediterranean region, including North Africa, Italy (including Sicily and Sardinia), countries of the former Yugoslavia (except Serbia and North Macedonia), Albania, Bulgaria, Romania, Greece, France, Spain, Portugal and Turkey (KARSHOLT & RAZOWSKI 1996) (Fig. 2). Flight time: August–September. The caterpillar feeds on grasses from October to May (RÁKOSY 1997).

There are several migrant species in the genera *Mythimna* Ochsenheimer, 1816 and *Leucania* Ochsenheimer, 1816, such as *Mythimna albipuncta* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775), *Mythimna l-album* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Mythimna vitellina* (Hübner, 1808), *Mythimna unipuncta* (Haworth, 1809) or *Leucania loreyi* (Duponchel, 1827) (VOJNITS 1966). Migrant species likely utilise river valleys for expansion; this kind of migration route is clearly presented by *Polypogon plumigeralis* (Hübner, 1825), which appeared in the last decade in Hungary (TÓTH *et al.* 2010). Similar phenomenon can be observed in the case of *Mythimna congrua* (Hübner, [1817]) (SUM & BENEDEK 2020). Considering these, the author's opinion is that the occurrence of *Leucania putrescens* in Hungary can be explained by ordinary migratory behaviour of the species rather than a result of climate change. *Leucania putrescens* is to be placed after *Leucania comma* (Linnaeus, 1761) in the Hungarian checklist (VARGA *et al.* 2004). Proposed Hungarian name: mediterrán rétibagoly.

Fig. 1. *Leucania putrescens* (Hübner, [1824]) (drawing by Csaba Szabóky)

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